

Dielectric design of ester-filled power transformers: AC stress analysis

Andrés Montero, Belén García, Juan Carlos Burgos, Carlos González-García

Abstract—In the last 20 years the use of ester fluids as an alternative to mineral oil for transformer insulation has been an active field of research and development. These liquids have a much lower environmental impact than mineral oils, besides reducing the transformer’s fire risk. Although the use of natural and synthetic esters is nowadays frequent for certain applications, as for distribution transformers in highly populated areas, railway transformers or off-shore windmill transformers, the experience on large and medium sized units is still reduced.

One of the critical aspects that must be assessed to use esters as dielectric fluids for large size transformers is the dielectric design of the equipment. The permittivity of esters and ester-impregnated cellulose are different from those of mineral-oil-cellulose systems, what has an impact on the electric field distribution in the transformer. Additionally, in some cases, the dielectric strength of ester fluids differs from that of mineral oil. This paper presents a study about the dielectric design of ester-based power transformers. The insulation system of a 400/138 kV, 280 MVA transformer was modelled using a finite element tool and a comparison of the field distribution under 50 Hz AC power voltage of both insulation systems is provided.

Keywords— Stress, electric fields, oil insulation, power transformer insulation, dielectric breakdown, design methodology

I. INTRODUCTION

Large and medium size transformers have used mineral oil (MO) as liquid insulation for more than 100 years. MO has a good performance both as an electrical insulation and as a cooling agent, furthermore it protects the cellulose insulation and has a crucial role in the diagnosis of transformers. However, in the last decades there has been a significant interest in developing and using alternative liquids which may improve the safety of the equipment and reduce their environmental impact. Among these alternative fluids, natural and synthetic esters are the ones that have obtained a higher attention and their use has increased exponentially since they were initially proposed in the nineties [1].

Natural and synthetic esters are biodegradable fluids; their use limits the environmental risk of the transformers and reduces the fluid’s disposal cost. For those reasons, esters are nowadays the main insulating liquids for some applications such as off-shore wind power transformers, transformers operating on ships and transformers for railway traction. Additionally, the flash point of esters are typically up to three times larger than the values of MO, what reduces the fire risk of ester-filled transformers and increases their safety. Thus, esters are suitable for transformers located in highly populated areas or next to critical infrastructures. Finally, the relatively high affinity of ester fluids for water displaces the moisture equilibrium towards the fluid lowering the water content in the solid insulation with the subsequent impact on the cellulose ageing rate.

Most of the experience accumulated with ester fluids has been related with transformers of small and medium sizes being their use in larger units still anecdotal. However, a growing number of experiences on large size units have been reported in the last years and it is expected that their use will spread in the future [2], [3].

Replacing the MO with a different insulating fluid has a clear impact on the transformer design. The thermal properties of esters

are different from those of MO; in particular, the viscosity of esters more than triples that of MO. The influence of this factor on the temperature distribution of ester-filled transformers has been studied by a number of authors who agree that the thermal design of ester-filled transformers should be reviewed to avoid an increase in transformer operating temperatures as the slower flow velocity of the coolant reduces the heat transfer rate [1]. However, it must be pointed out that there is also debate about the impact of operating temperature on the life expectancy of ester-impregnated solid insulation. Several authors have provided experimental evidence on the fact that the ageing rate of cellulose could be softened in presence of esters [4], [5], suggesting that higher hottest-spot temperatures could be admissible in ester-filled units.

The use of ester fluids as liquid insulation of transformers has also an impact on the dielectric design of the equipment. A large number of works have compared the dielectric properties of MO and those of natural and synthetic esters concluding that, although there are only small differences between the behaviour of both fluids under quasi-uniform fields at the same gap, the differences are larger for higher field inhomogeneity and/or longer gaps. Under these conditions esters are more susceptible to the development of fast and energetic discharges and show lower dielectric strengths [6], [7]. This aspect must be taken into account when designing the insulating system of an ester-filled transformer. The dielectric properties of natural and synthetic esters are quite similar [6], [7] and the selection of one of those liquids will depend on other criteria such as oxidation stability, ageing, availability, cost etc.

Another factor that has an impact on the transformer insulation design is the fact that the permittivity of esters is typically about a 50% higher than that of MO [8]. As the difference between the permittivity of the liquid and the one of the solid insulation is closer, the electric field distribution of ester-filled transformers becomes more homogeneous and the stress in the ester is lower than the stress that would appear in a similar insulation system when MO is used. This is a beneficial aspect as the fluid is at the same time the element with a lower dielectric strength of the oil-paper insulating system and the one that is typically subjected to a higher stress.

This paper investigates the impact of using natural esters (NE) as liquid insulation on the dielectric design of power transformers. A finite element analysis (FEM) is carried out on a 280 MVA transformer. The field distribution and the insulation design criteria are compared when MO or NE are used as insulating fluid. General conclusions are extracted that can be of application for the dielectric design of NE-filled transformers. The obtained results might be extrapolated to synthetic ester filled transformers, since the properties of both fluids are similar.

II. TRANSFORMER INSULATION SYSTEM

The transformer insulation system is composed of liquid and solid insulation. Transformer liquid insulation fills the transformer tank and impregnates the solid insulation providing electrical insulation across the whole transformer volume. Additionally, the insulating fluid acts as a cooling agent. Oil channels are included in the transformer design to guarantee an adequate oil flow throughout the active part and to allow a sufficient dissipation of the heat produced by the power losses.

The solid insulation comprises the thin insulation, which is commonly constituted by Kraft paper that wounds the conductors, and the

thick insulation which consist of barriers and spacers of pressboard (Fig. 1). The spacers are support elements which are located between adjacent disks or other elements of the transformer to form the oil-circulation ducts and provide mechanical support to the transformer. The barriers are basic elements for the dielectric design of the transformer. They divide highly stressed oil channels into smaller gaps increasing the dielectric strength of transformer regions that are subjected to high electric stress [9], as the dielectric performance of liquids is nonlinear. The performance of the whole insulating system is determined by the design of the barrier system.

Fig. 1. Transformer solid insulation.

Among the different materials that constitute the insulation system of a transformer, the liquid insulation must be regarded as the weakest element under electric fields. On the one hand, oils present much lower dielectric strength than oil-impregnated cellulose materials. Besides, the permittivity of oil is significantly lower than the permittivity of oil-impregnated cellulose ($\epsilon_{oil} < \epsilon_{pb}$), what affects the field distribution between both materials appearing the higher levels of stress in the former (Fig. 2).

The breakdown process of an insulating liquid starts when a certain volume of the liquid is ionized; the initial ionization may locally enhance the electric field within the liquid, giving rise to further molecular ionization which derives in the formation of a streamer. The streamer progresses throughout the oil accelerating particles, ions and negative charges present in the fluid what increases even more the local electric field until an electron avalanche takes place which provokes the total breakdown of the liquid. It must be noted that the streamer always have its origin in some impurity or defect present in the insulating liquid. As the volume of the liquid subjected to a certain stress becomes larger, the presence of defects that could trigger the streamer process is more likely, what increases the probability of breakdown and reduces the breakdown voltage. To avoid this effect, large oil volumes are subdivided within transformers into smaller gaps which are separated by pressboard barriers.

Fig. 2. Field distribution inside a flat parallel plate capacitor.

Other critical elements within the transformer insulation system are the interfaces between oil and solid insulation. Arcs may be formed along the surface of pressboard barriers if the gradient of electric potential between a couple of points exceeds certain values. To limit the risk of creepage, barriers of large lengths are avoided in regions of the transformer subjected to high tangential electric stress.

III. DESIGN OF THE INSULATION SYSTEM OF MINERAL-OIL FILLED TRANSFORMERS

A. Insulation design criteria

The design of the insulation system of a transformer is based on the evaluation of the electrical stress that appears in the different regions of the dielectric materials that compose the transformer insulation when they are subjected to certain stresses. A geometry is defined for the oil-cellulose insulation which guarantees that the electrical stress produced during the factory testing is withstood by its different parts with a low enough probability of failure.

Transformer factory testing includes three types of electrical tests [10], aimed at reproducing the overvoltages the equipment might be subjected to during operation:

- Applied voltage at power frequency test, which allows to check the ability of the insulation located between adjacent windings or between the windings and the tank or the core to withstand overvoltages.
- Induced voltage test, to verify the turn to turn insulation at the operating voltage, and also line to ground and line to line insulation at approximately 180% of rated operating voltage.
- Switching and lightning impulses, to check the insulation between disks and the large oil volumes under very fast transients.

The design of a transformer commonly involves the use of models implemented in a FEM software to calculate the distribution of electric field that results when those stresses are applied to the transformer. An initial configuration is defined for the different elements and materials that constitute the transformer insulation system (i.e. number, position and thickness of the solid barriers, thickness of the paper covering the electrodes...). Subsequently the initial configuration is modified to assure that the design criteria are met for four types of regions: surface of electrodes, small oil gaps, pressboard barriers and large oil volumes. The insulation design criteria are defined by each individual manufacturer and are not public, but some general information on the topic is provided next.

B. Maximum local stress at the surface of electrodes

In order to avoid damages on the surface of the electrode or the inception of partial discharges in the Kraft paper that wraps the windings, the maximum local stress at the surface of an electrode should not exceed a certain value, which is typically about 11-12 kV/mm for insulated electrodes and below 2 kV/mm for un-insulated electrodes or ground planes. The maximum local field is influenced by the geometry of the electrodes and by the applied voltage [11].

C. Breakdown in small oil gaps

The electrical stress across the small oil gaps must be lower than the oil dielectric strength, which depends on the width of the gap and on whether the electrode is insulated or not.

Empirical curves have been proposed, and are widely accepted by the transformer industry, which provide the values of the electric field that guarantees a low probability of inception of partial discharges in a certain oil duct. Fig. 3 shows the curves developed by the insulation manufacturer Weidmann for MO gap lengths between 0.1 and 250 mm for a discharge inception probability below 1% with uniform electric field during AC test (1 minute, 50 Hz).

All the small gaps across the transformer insulation must meet the adopted design criteria. Adding a new barrier is a solution when the actual stress across a gap exceeds the admissible value, since the oil strength increases for short distances.

Fig. 3. Weidmann Design Curves of low probability for discharge inception in MO gaps. Reproduced from [8].

D. Creepage along pressboard barriers

To guarantee a low risk of creepage in the interfaces between oil and pressboard barriers, it must be assessed that the gradient of the tangential electric field throughout those solid barriers is below certain values. The creepage risk is evaluated with curves as the one shown in Fig. 4, which provides the maximum tangential stress withstood by the solid insulation (i.e. probability of failure below 1%), when a pressboard barrier of a given length is subjected to a certain voltage gradient of AC power frequency during 1 minute.

Fig. 4. Weidmann Creep Curve. Reproduced from [8]

E. Breakdown in large oil volumes

For the dielectric design of regions with large oil gaps, as the spaces that appear in clearances between leads and ground or between adjacent leads, the stressed oil volume (SOV) theory is commonly used [11], [12] to calculate the maximum electric stress withstood by a certain oil volume with low probability of failure. Several empirical equations have been proposed to calculate that maximum field [12],

[13], [14]. Siodla [14] proposes (1) to determine the maximum electric field withstood by a certain oil volume for power frequency voltage applied for one minute:

$$E = 18.343 \cdot SOV^{-0.155} \quad (kV/mm) \quad (1)$$

where SOV is the stressed oil volume in cm^3 .

The SOV is typically calculated as the region in which the calculated electric stress values vary between the maximum value and the 90% of it. Nevertheless, a recent study [15] suggests that it is more accurate to define the SOV as the region of the space where the electric field is above the 70% of the maximum electric field. The latter is the criterion that will be adopted in further sections of the paper.

IV. DIELECTRIC DESIGN OF ESTER-FILLED TRANSFORMERS

To understand the impact of using a NE instead of MO as transformer liquid insulation two factors must be regarded: the difference in the relative permittivity of the liquid and the liquid-impregnated cellulose and the variation of the breakdown criteria for the different materials. The former property impacts on the field distribution along the insulation system, while the latter is related to the maximum stress withstood by a combination of insulating materials. Although differences between the properties of NE and MO are still a topic of research, some typical values are provided in this section.

A. Relative permittivity of the oil-paper insulation system

In [8] values are reported for the permittivity of different types of solid and liquid insulation based in MO and in NE. Those values were experimentally obtained at temperatures 25, 90 and 130 °C. Table I provides the values of the permittivities of a MO and a NE, and those of Kraft paper, and pressboard of different densities when impregnated with MO or NE. The values correspond to a temperature 25°C. As can be seen, the permittivity of the NE is closer to the permittivity of the ester-impregnated solid insulation than the permittivity of MO and that of the MO-impregnated cellulose. This fact allows for a more homogeneous distribution of the electrical stress in the oil-paper insulation system and as a consequence the fluid will be less stressed. This is a positive aspect, since, as it discussed before, the fluid is the weakest part of the transformer insulation.

TABLE I
DIELECTRIC CONSTANT OF MO, NE BASED MATERIALS AT AMBIENT TEMPERATURE. DATA TAKEN FROM [8]

	Pure fluid	Kraft paper	Low density pressb.	High density pressb.
MO	2.4	3.9	3.9	4.5
NE	3.3	4.6	4.4	4.6

Due to the difference in the dielectric permittivities of insulating fluids and impregnated pressboard, NE brings advantages in regions where the electric field is more homogeneous. However, in those areas with a great inhomogeneity in the field distribution, such as the winding ends, the maximum stress value at the interfaces between solid and liquid insulation could be higher in NE than in MO [16]. Differences may also be found in nonuniform fields and long gap distances [17].

B. Insulation design criteria for NE based insulation

Although the design process of ester filled transformers is based on the same principles as for MO filled transformers, there are differences between the dielectric strength of both fluids that makes it

necessary to change some of the design criteria depending on whether the insulating fluid is a NE instead of MO.

In [18] an AC breakdown voltage study is presented showing that there is almost no difference between the dielectric strength of MO and NE for oil gaps smaller than 20 mm. Other authors present similar results when comparing NE and MO in small gaps [8], [19]. According to these results, it is possible to apply the design curves shown in Fig. 3 for small oil gaps in NE-based insulation.

However, the breakdown voltages reported for oil gaps of widths larger than 20 mm are in general lower for NE than for MO [18].

The differences between the breakdown process in large volumes of MO and NE is a topic that is still under research. One of the most studied aspects is related with the influence of the field homogeneity in the breakdown voltage of ester fluids [18]. The field homogeneity is quantified by means of the "Schwaiger factor" or "inhomogeneity factor" (η), which is defined as the ratio between the mean and the maximum field strength (2).

$$\eta = E_{mean}/E_{max} \quad (2)$$

In [18], [20] a variety of experimental tests aimed at relating the measured breakdown voltage values with the field inhomogeneity factor are described. In these studies several insulating liquids were tested considering different electrode configurations (sphere, needle, blunt point), different gap distances and voltage waveshapes. Values of the field inhomogeneity factor lower than 0.1 indicate that the field distribution is inhomogeneous. Studies conclude that the dielectric strength depends on the gap width and on the homogeneity of the electric field. In the case of AC stress with similar levels of inhomogeneity the difference between the dielectric strength of MOs and NEs mainly reflects the liquid quality like moisture or particle contamination, but some studies reports differences up to 20% [21]; in the case of impulse overvoltages the difference rises until 35%.

Regarding creep breakdown voltage, a comprehensive study is presented by T. Prevost in [8] which compares of the dielectric performance of MO and NE impregnated pressboard barriers, concluding that both liquids present almost identical values of breakdown stress for the same creep distances and that NE impregnated pressboard verifies the creep curve shown in Fig. 4.

V. CASE OF STUDY

A. Transformer under study

A 400/138 kV 280 MVA transformer designed with an insulation of MO was modelled with the FEM software Comsol Multiphysics.

The transformer is a three legged core-type unit with three concentric windings in each leg. The low voltage winding (LV) is the inner one, the high voltage winding (HV) is located in the middle and the regulation-high voltage winding is in the outer side. Both, the HV and the regulation windings are split-type windings. Table II provides some constructive details of the transformer under study.

TABLE II
MAIN PARAMETERS OF THE TRANSFORMER UNDER STUDY

Rated voltage	400/138 kV
Rated power	280 MVA
Frequency	50 Hz
Number of phases	3
Cooling type	ODAF
Transformer Connection Group	YNyn0
Winding type	Disks
Number of LV disks	96
Number of HV disks	116
Number of regulation disks	20
Maximum voltage (kV)	420

B. Scope of the study

The aim of the study is to evaluate the reduction in the dielectric margin when the insulating fluid MO is replaced by NE, for a certain insulation design. In the following sections the electric field distribution of the transformer is calculated considering the two insulating fluids and afterwards the compliance of the design criteria described in section IV-B is discussed.

As explained before, the design process of the transformer insulation is focused on withstanding the stresses to which it is subjected during dielectric tests: the power frequency applied voltage test, the induced voltage tests and the switching and lightning tests. The present study focuses on the first one. The impact of using a NE as dielectric fluid on the switching and lightning impulse test and on the induced voltage test will be addressed in the future, for a comprehensive study of the electric field distribution of the total insulation system using NE instead of MO.

Standard IEC 60076-3 [10] states that during the AC power frequency voltage test only the winding under consideration is energized whereas the other windings remain grounded. It is worth noting that in the transformer under study, the HV and regulation windings are connected in series to each other, so both are energized.

C. Finite element model

1) *Geometry*: As explained before, the transformer design process evaluates the field distribution both in small gaps and in large oil volumes. To study both cases, two sections of the transformer were modelled in the FEM software: a 2D axisymmetric model, which represents one of the three windings and the insulation system inside the window of the transformer, and another 2D model of the upper part of the transformer tank, focused on the connection of the HV winding with the bushing.

The analysis of the a 3D modeling can be replaced by a "worst case" 2D modeling, where the 2D stress on the ring is intentionally enhanced by the 2D model. Safety margin results would be on safe side and of similar impact either for MO or for NEs

The insulation system was designed in order to fulfill MO criteria with security margin above 20%.

The insulation meets some general specifications [13]: all the oil barriers have a minimal thickness of 2 mm for getting good mechanical stability; the width of oil gaps is no larger than 12 mm; the width of the oil gap between the winding and the first barrier has a minimum value of 6 mm due to thermal considerations; the static end rings (SER) resemble a disk as much as possible and have an insulation paper thickness around 3 mm with a minimum outer radius 6 mm, and finally the Kraft paper wrapping the lead between the winding and the bushing has a minimal thickness of 30 mm in both sides.

The geometry of the model implemented to study the small gaps is shown in Fig. 5. As can be seen the model is an axisymmetric representation of the core window and the three windings placed in a transformer leg. In order to simplify the geometry of the model, the windings are modelled as continuous disks instead of considering the real number of turns per disk. This simplification is adequate for the simulation of the applied voltage test but it is not suitable for the analysis of the induced voltage test, which will be tackled in a future work. The permittivities considered for the different materials are those shown in Table I.

Large volume analysis are carried out with the 2D model of Fig. 6, which is a plane cross section by the centre of a limb and the HV bushing. There are other areas of the transformer susceptible to be studied such as a neutral lead, regions with long clearances or aluminium pipes. However the HV lead exit through the bushing has been chosen in this work for the study of large oil volumes.

The analysis of the electric field at the HV lead exit and the bushing would be more accurate if a 3D model was used. However, since the objective of the study is to compare the behaviour of MO and NE, the 3D modeling was replaced by a "worst case" 2D modeling, where the 2D stress on the shield is intentionally enhanced

Fig. 5. Model to study small oil gaps

by the 2D model. The safety margin results obtained in the study are on safe side, but with similar impact either for MO or for NE.

Core and windings of one phase are represented along with the lead that connects the HV winding with the grid through the bushing. The bushing was modelled as a porcelain with an external layer of oil and some layers of aluminium foil with oil-impregnated kraft-paper in between, to represent the capacitive control of the bushing, and a aluminium shield at the bottom as is typically assembled in transformers of this rated voltage [22], [23], [24]. Some manufacturers place a aluminium ring connected to ground at the intersection of the turret which house bushings and the transformer tank, in order to reduce the stress of the oil in that region of the transformer due to the presence of sharp angles in the tank. In this study, that aluminium ring and the bushing shield are both included and they are considered to be bare; the lead is wrapped in Kraft paper.

Fig. 6. Cross-section of the upper part of the transformer

2) *Boundary conditions:* In order to simulate the power frequency voltage test as described in IEC Std 60076-3:2013 [10] all the disks of the HV winding and the regulation winding are subjected to the same voltage while the LV windings, the core and the tank remain grounded. According to Section 7 of IEC Std 60076-3:2013, the voltage between the tested terminal and ground is 510 kV for a HV winding whose maximum voltage is 420 kV (Table II).

For large volume analysis, conditions are the same as before, and the lead is at the voltage level of the HV winding (510 kV). The outer layer of the capacitive control of the bushing is connected to

ground, whereas the potential of the other layers will be assigned by COMSOL during the simulation; and the shield of the bushing is also connected to the potential of the lead (510 kV). The concentric aluminium ring of the bushing is grounded as the tank and the core. The boundary conditions considered for the bushing are summarized in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Boundary conditions considered for the bottom part of the bushing

3) *Differential equations:* Comsol Multiphysics calculates the electric field in each node of the mesh starting from Gauss' equation which relates electric displacement, \mathbf{D} , to the total charge density ρ and the constitutive relation for a linear, homogeneous and isotropic material which relates \mathbf{D} to electric field intensity, \mathbf{E} , through dielectric permittivity (3).

$$\varepsilon_0 \varepsilon_r \nabla \mathbf{E} = \rho \quad (3)$$

Finally, the electric scalar potential, V , in steady state follows the relation (4):

$$\mathbf{E} = -\nabla V \quad (4)$$

Once implemented the model and selected the boundary conditions, a 'free triangular mesh', automatically generated by Comsol, is used to define the nodes for the simulation.

VI. RESULTS

As explained before, the applied voltage test was simulated in Comsol Multiphysics considering a frequency 50 Hz. The analysis of the small oil gaps, creepage and large oil volumes was carried out obtaining the electric field distribution and verifying the compliance of the design criteria when the insulating fluid is MO or NE.

The safety margin is calculated comparing the calculated cumulative stress of each region, with the industry curves. The safety margin is calculated for each analysis as:

$$\text{Safety margin}(\%) = \frac{X_{ref} - X_{calculated}}{X_{ref}} \cdot 100 \quad (5)$$

where X_{ref} is the maximum allowable working stress for the considered variable and $X_{calculated}$ is the value calculated in the simulation.

A. Small gap analysis

Simulations of the model of Fig. 5 show that the regions of maximum stress within the transformer insulation are located at both

ends of the windings, specially in the outer corners of the SER. As the windings are not centered in the axial direction of the transformer leg the electric field distribution is not equal at both ends and the bottom HV SER is the most stressed region due to the lower distance to the bottom yoke. The analysis presented next is focused on this area.

Fig. 8 compares the electric field distribution at the bottom the winding when the insulation is MO and when is NE. As can be seen, fluids and solid insulation are subjected to different stresses because of the different values of the permittivity of MO and NE as mentioned in section II. The difference between the two insulating liquids is appreciated in the Kraft paper that wraps the SER, which is more stressed in the case of the NE-based insulation.

Fig. 8. Electric field distribution at the bottom of the window for MO (left) and NE (right)

Regarding the assessment of the electrical stress in the oil gaps, the industry practice was considered, which consists of evaluating the cumulative value of the field across trajectories within the maximum stressed region [11]. These values are used to check the compliance with the design criterion established in the Weidmann curves.

Fig. 9a shows the electric field distribution in the most stressed oil-gap represented through trajectory (AB) when the insulating fluid is MO or NE. Different zones can be distinguished in Fig. 9a: green area indicates the field distribution in the paper Kraft, pink area represent the first pressboard-barrier and blue areas represent the stress in the fluid.

The cumulative average stress, calculated for the trajectory AB of Fig. 9a, is plotted in Fig 9b for MO and NE. The maximum strength specified by Weidmann curves (Fig. 3) is also plotted in the figure. Since the gap width is below 20 mm, Weidmann curves are also valid for NE, as explained in section IV-B. The dielectric design is considered adequate if the strength curve is above the stress curves for all gap distances. In the case studied in this work the most stressed gap width is 7 mm, and the accumulated field for MO and for NE is always lower than the dielectric strength. The accumulated stress is lower for NE than for MO, thus the design criterion is achieved with a wider security margin if the liquid insulation is NE.

For safety margin calculation, the studied trajectory is discretized, and a margin is obtained for each point according to eq. (5). The average safety margin was 31.1% for MO and 34.9% for NE.

Fig. 9a also shows that the electric field distribution is more homogeneous in case of NE-based insulation. The difference between maximum and minimum field on the line is 4.27 kV/mm for MO (ΔE_{MO}) and 2.95 kV/mm in the case of the NE (ΔE_{NE}), i.e. a 30.1% lower.

Kraft paper and pressboard barriers are more stressed when the fluid is a NE, while the fluid is subjected to a lower electric field. A direct consequence of the above is related to the maximum stress at the electrode surface. The highest electric field in the Kraft paper next to the electrode surface occurs in the bottom SER of HV winding. Therefore maximum stress in the paper criterion gives worst results for transformers with NE than for transformers with MO (this is also shown in Fig. 8) due to the homogenization of the electric field within the insulation system. The results are presented in Table III.

(a) Field distribution

(b) Cumulative electric field

Fig. 9. Small gap analysis

Both results are below the admissible limit of 11 kV/mm but the safety margin in the case of NE is lower than 20% .

TABLE III
MAXIMUM STRESS AT THE ELECTRODE SURFACE

	MO	NE
Max. stress (kV/mm)	8.34	9.11
Limit stress (kV/mm)	11	11
Safety margin (%)	24.18	17.18

B. Creepage

The creepage design criterion is checked from the tangential stress on the surfaces of the solid barriers. As in the previous analysis, the most stressed part is located at the bottom of the window. Tangential electric field distribution is calculated as the projection of the electric field vector on the pressboard barriers with a significant tangential stress, both for vertical barriers (axial field component) and for horizontal barriers (radial field component).

When the vertical creepage is analyzed along the length of a pressboard barrier that covers the entire winding, the value of the tangential stress is almost zero in the central zone of the cylinder.

Therefore, the representative area for this study is the region where a higher tangential field appears due to the fringing effect. This region is highlighted in red in the lower-right image of Fig. 10a. Two vertical pressboard barriers are analyzed because they show significant tangential stress that could cause creepage.

Fig. 10 shows the results of the tangential electric field distribution along the surface of the vertical pressboard barriers and the horizontal pressboard barriers in the case of MO-based insulation and NE-based insulation. The horizontal creepage analysis shows that the variation of the horizontal creep (i.e. the radial projection of the electric field over the pressboard barrier) is greater next to the corner of the SER than in the middle of the winding. However, because of its short length, the analysed zone for this calculation is the complete barrier in radial direction (Fig. 10b). As can be seen, the tangential electric field distribution along the surface of the barriers is practically identical for MO and NE based systems, both for vertical and horizontal barriers.

(a) Vertical tangential electric field

(b) Horizontal tangential electric field

Fig. 10. Creepage analysis

To check the creepage design criterion, the cumulative tangential electric field is compared to the creep Weidmann curve (Fig. 4). As discussed before, although the curve was developed for MO-based insulation it is valid for NE-based insulation as well.

According to the simulations of the vertical creepage for the two analyzed pressboard barriers, the cumulative stress is lower than the creep values provided by Weidmann curve. The calculated safety

margin is 71.5% for the shortest barrier (numbered as 1 in Fig. 10a) and 36.4% for the largest one (numbered as 2). For the horizontal creepage evaluation, the cumulative stress is also lower than the creep strength and the safety margin is 71%. The results for both fluids are very similar and the safety margins obtained for both fluids are the same.

C. Large oil volume analysis

As an example of large oil stressed volumes analysis, this section shows the study of the electric field distribution for both MO and NE in the model of Fig. 6. The simulation of that geometry for MO and NE showed that the maximum electric field is located around the bushing shield. Fig. 11 shows the field distribution of that region when MO acts as insulating fluid. The results are very similar for the case of NE.

Fig. 11. Electric field distribution at the bushing region and SOV for MO.

Table IV shows the maximum electric field obtained in the region of study, the value of the SOV for the case of MO and NE insulated transformer and the maximum admissible stress for both insulation systems. The oil volume considered for the calculations was the clearance between the bushing shield and the tank, which has a mean gap between electrodes of around 600 mm. As explained in section III. B, the dielectric strength of large volumes of MO can be calculated with eq. (1) obtaining a value of 13.85 kV/mm for the tested configuration.

In the case of NE, research on the design criteria for large gaps is still scarce and there is no agreement on a design criterion that can be applied for such regions. Haegle [18], [20] relates that the difference between both fluids depends mainly on the degree of inhomogeneity of the electric field and on the electrode distance. The inhomogeneity factor η calculated for the studied geometry according to eq. (2) was 0.125 for MO and 0.124 for NE. Those levels of inhomogeneity indicate that the electric field is quasi-inhomogeneous for both fluids. Hagge [18] compares the dielectric breakdown of NE and MO for different inhomogeneity factors and electrode distances within 20 to 50 mm. For values of η of 0.12 and sphere-sphere electrode with distance 50 mm, the author reports that the breakdown voltage of the NE is a 13% lower than that of the MO. As the electrode distance in the case of this study is larger, a reduction of a 20% was considered for the breakdown strength of NE, obtaining a dielectric strength of 11.14 kV for this material.

As it can be seen in Table IV, both MO and NE fulfill the design criteria for this region, since the maximum electric field is lower

than the dielectric strength for both liquids. However, the use of NE reduces the safety margin by 30% compared to MO. This result evidences that the design of transformers immersed in NE may differ, in some aspects, from that of MO-immersed units. Additionally, if a transformer designed for MO is intended to be used with NE, large clearances must be carefully studied to avoid the appearance of critical points and weaknesses in the liquid insulation.

TABLE IV
LARGE OIL VOLUME ANALYSIS FOR MO AND NE

	SOV (cm ³)	E _{max} (kV/mm)	Strength (kV/mm)	Safety marg.(%)
MO	6.12	7.55	13.85	45.49
NE	5.9	7.61	11.14	31.69

VII. CONCLUSIONS

From the performed study it can be concluded that the dielectric design of a MO immersed transformer can be used with a NE without major modifications in the insulation system except in cases where the dielectric margin is very low.

The weakest points of the insulation system in the NE-based transformer are the large oil gaps, in which the safety margin decreases by almost 30%, although the electric field values are similar in both fluids. This is due to the fact that the NE has significantly lower dielectric strength than MO for large electrode distances.

Another critical point is the surface of the SER electrode, since the electric field in the Kraft paper increases when a NE is used as liquid insulation.

On the other hand, the small oil gaps are less stressed in that case. Safety margins obtained for small oil volumes are improved if NE is used as liquid insulation. Finally, it was observed that the creepage risk is very similar for both fluids, and almost identical field gradients and safety margins were obtained for both cases in this study.

Although the present study focuses on the analysis of NEs the results could be extrapolated to synthetic esters, since both materials have similar permittivity and dielectric strength [6] [7].

It should be noted that this work refers only to the behavior of the insulation system subjected to AC stress. In order to have a full understanding of the problem the behavior against lightning impulse must be evaluated. This will be tackled in a future study.

VIII. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported in part by the Spanish State Research Agency under Grant PID2019-107126RB-C21/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and in part by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Program, under Grant 823969. The authors acknowledge Dr. Qiang Liu, from Manchester University, for his valuable advice.

REFERENCES

- [1] R et al. Martin. Experiences in service with new insulating liquids. *CIGRE Working Group A2.35*, (436):1–95, 2010.
- [2] K. J Rapp, J. Luksich, and A. Sbravati. Application of Natural Ester Insulating Liquids in Power Transformers. *Proceedings of My Transfo*, (November):1–7, 2014.
- [3] M. Cuesto, C. González-García, D. Vukovic, J. Emmel, A. Aznar, J.C. Sánchez, and P. Gómez. Largest single-phase green transformer with natural ester at 420 kV and tests comparison with mineral oil. *CIGRE Study Committee A2 Colloquium*, (November):1–11, 2017.
- [4] T.V. Oommen. Vegetable oils for liquid-filled transformers. *IEEE Electr. Insul. Mag.*, 18(1):6–11, 2002.
- [5] Belen García, Tamara García, Victor Primo, Juan Carlos Burgos, and Domingo Urquiza. Studying the loss of life of natural-ester-filled transformer insulation: impact of moisture on the aging rate of paper. *IEEE Electrical Insulation Magazine*, 33(1):15–23, 2017.

- [6] Zijia Shen, Feipeng Wang, Zhiqing Wang, and Jian Li. A critical review of plant-based insulating fluids for transformer: 30-year development. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 141:110783, 2021.
- [7] U. Mohan Rao, I. Fofana, A. Beroual, P. Rozga, M. Pompili, L. Calcara, and Kevin J. Rapp. A review on pre-breakdown phenomena in ester fluids: Prepared by the international study group of IEEE deis liquid dielectrics technical committee. *IEEE Transactions on Dielectrics and Electrical Insulation*, 27(5):1546–1560, 2020.
- [8] T. A. Prevost. Dielectric properties of natural esters and their influence on transformer insulation system design and performance — an update. In *2009 IEEE Power Energy Society General Meeting*, pages 1–7, 2009.
- [9] V. Dahinden, K. Schultz, and A. Küchler. Function of solid insulation in transformers. *Transform 98*, (chapter 2):1–14, 1998.
- [10] International Standard IEC 60076-3. Power transformers - Part 3: Insulation levels, dielectric tests and external clearances in air, 2013.
- [11] W. Ziomek, K. Vijayan, D. Boyd, K. Kubly, and M. Franchek. High voltage power transformer insulation design. In *2011 Electrical Insulation Conf. (EIC)*, pages 211–215, 2011.
- [12] Robert Vecchio, Bertrand Poulin, Pierre Feghali, Dilipkumar Shah, and Rajendra Ahuja. *Transformer Design Principles: With Applications to Core-Form Power Transformers*. 01 2001.
- [13] S.V. Kulkarni and S.A. Khararde. *Transformer Engineering*. 05 2004.
- [14] K. Siodla, W. Ziomek, and E. Kuffel. The volume and area effect in transformer oil. *Conference Record of IEEE International Symposium on Electrical Insulation*, pages 359–362, 2002.
- [15] P. Gabrić, A. Orešković, V. Kuprešanin, A. Mikulecky, and V. Podobnik. Stressed oil volume theory in transformer winding corner stress analysis. *Lecture Notes in Electrical Engineering*, 671(October):33–43, 2020.
- [16] M. Lashbrook, A. Gyore, and R. Martin. Review of the electrical and thermal behaviour of ester-based dielectric liquids for extra high voltage applications. In *2017 INSUCON - 13th Int. Electrical Insulation Conf. (INSUCON)*, pages 1–6, 2017.
- [17] T. B. Marchesan and A. J. Fanchin. Natural ester fluid: The transformer design perspective. In *2010 IEEE/PES Transmission and Distribution Conf. and Exposition: Latin America (T D-LA)*, pages 329–333, 2010.
- [18] S. Haegle, S. Tenbohlen, R. Fritsche, K. Rapp, and A. Sbravati. Characterization of inhomogeneous field breakdown in natural ester liquid compared to mineral oil. In *2016 IEEE Int. Conf. on High Voltage Engineering and Application (ICHVE)*, pages 1–5, 2016.
- [19] C.G. Azcarraga, A. Cavallini, U. Piovan, B. Poulin, D.M. Shah, and R. Ahuja. A comparison of the voltage withstand properties of ester and mineral oils. *IEEE Electr. Insul. Mag.*, 30(5):6–14, 2014.
- [20] S. Haegle, F. Vahidi, S. Tenbohlen, K. J. Rapp, and A. Sbravati. Lightning impulse withstand of natural ester liquid. *Energies*, 11(8):1–13, 2018.
- [21] Q. Liu. Electrical performance of ester liquids under impulse voltage for application in power transformers. 2011.
- [22] M. H. Zink, V. Klipfel, F. Berger, and A. Küchler. Ageing-condition assessment of generator transformer bushings by means of dielectric simulation models. In *2012 IEEE International Conference on Condition Monitoring and Diagnosis*, pages 137–140, 2012.
- [23] Azam Nekahi, Brian G. Stewart, and Scott G. McMeekin. Electric field distribution on the outer surface of lower porcelain of an oil transformer bushing-accumulation of metal-contained colloid. In *2015 IEEE 11th International Conference on the Properties and Applications of Dielectric Materials (ICPADM)*, pages 632–635, 2015.
- [24] Li Xining, Tang Hao, Yang Fan, Cheng Huanchao, and Zhang Shuqi. The influence of temperature on draw rod system of converter transformer grid side bushing. In *2021 International Conference on Electrical Materials and Power Equipment (ICEMPE)*, pages 1–4, 2021.

with biodegradable fluids.

Andrés Montero (BSc'17, M'20) was born in Cuenca in 1995. In 2017, he obtained a B.Sc. Degree in Industrial Engineering from Universidad Politécnica de Valencia, Spain, and in 2020 a M.Sc. Degree in Industrial Engineering from Universidad Politécnica de Valencia and M.Sc. Degree in Electrical Engineering from Politecnico di Milano, Italy. Since 2020 he has been a Ph.D. student in the Electrical Engineering Department of Universidad Carlos III de Madrid. His main topic of interest is the study of the retrofilling process of transformers

Belén García (BSc 98 PhD'02) received the M.Sc. Degree in Physics from Universidad Complutense de Madrid in 1998, and the Ph.D. in Electrical Engineering from Universidad Carlos III de Madrid in 2002. Since 2004 she has held a Senior Lecturer position in the Electrical Engineering Dept. of the same university. Her main research interests are power transformer life management and insulating materials.

Juan Carlos Burgos (Bsc 80, PhD 87) received the PhD degree from the Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingenieros Industriales de Madrid in 1987. Currently, he is an Senior Lecturer in Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, Spain, where he has worked since 1994. His main research interest area is power transformer maintenance.

Carlos Gonzalez (BSc 04, MSc 06, PhD 2012) Carlos Gonzalez-García received the M.Sc. Degree in Industrial Engineering from Universidad Carlos III de Madrid in 2008, and the Ph.D. in Electrical Engineering from Universidad Carlos III de Madrid in 2012. He works on transformer manufacturing since 2013. His main research interests are power transformer design and testing.